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A MODERN APPROACH TO TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to modern methods and approaches to teaching a foreign language, their impact on the learning process and student results. The article analyzes the communicative approach, integration of modern technologies, individual methods and development of intercultural communication competence in foreign language lessons and considers the results.*

Keywords. *Foreign language, modern methods, communicative approach, technologies in education, individualization of learning, intercultural, communication, competence, teaching foreign languages.*

Introduction. In our dynamic information society, the process of teaching foreign languages has undergone significant changes. In today's world, where globalization and the associated cultural and economic interactions play an important role, knowledge of a foreign language is more important than ever. In this context, teaching German, one of the most widespread and influential languages in Europe, is of particular importance. Today's students live in an era when, thanks to the development of modern technologies, access to information

and education has become much more free and diverse. Students are now not limited to textbooks and lectures in the classroom, but can use interactive online resources, mobile applications, video conferencing and other tools that make learning a foreign language more convenient and interesting.

Main text. An important aspect of the modern approach to teaching a foreign language is also the emphasis on multilingualism and multicultural education. Students learn language and culture in parallel, communicating with native speakers. This creates a deeper understanding of foreign culture and helps to develop intercultural competencies. Many educators emphasize that organizing an interactive lesson through innovative technologies forces students to think independently, create and research, constantly maintains students' interest in knowledge during the learning process, and these are the peculiarities of the pedagogical cooperation process. This collaborative free lesson is certainly another important aspect of foreign language teaching.

We will discuss the fundamental principles of foreign language teaching, various methods of language teaching, as well as the impact of technology integration on the English language teaching process. An important aspect of the analysis is the digitalization of education in Uzbekistan and the development of professional competence of English teachers in modern educational conditions.

Below we will consider an analysis of various methods and resources based on the practical experience of teachers and students in teaching English.

- Integration of modern technical means: The use of online resources and digital tools in the educational process allows students to learn more interactively and effectively. Online platforms provide access to a variety of materials, including audio and video content.

- Developing communication skills: A communicative approach to learning helps develop the ability to communicate in English. Students learn to listen and

understand through audio-visual aids and to express their thoughts and ideas in this way, using phrases in dialogues and role-playing games.

- **Integration of cultural aspects:** The study of English culture and traditions becomes an integral part of education. The introduction of slides, subtitled films and short video lessons on customs, holidays helps students understand the language in a broader context and develop intercultural competence.

- **Individualized approach:** The use of an individualized curriculum allows you to take into account the different needs of students. This contributes to more effective learning and better results.

Studying English culture and history allows students to better understand the language in context and develop intercultural competence. This is becoming increasingly important in today's world. It is worth noting that a lesson that focuses on communication skills and the use of language in a real environment shows significant advantages. Students who participate in dialogues, role-playing, organizing real situations and other communicative exercises demonstrate a high level of language competence in communicating in English.

In conclusion, modern technologies are becoming an integral part of modern education. Therefore, modern methods require continuous professional development from teachers. Teachers should be ready to integrate technology into lessons, adapt teaching materials and create a stimulating learning environment, as well as be able to stimulate the needs and expectations of students in adapting to a changing environment.

In general, a modern approach to teaching English, that is, using multimedia in lessons, organizing lessons focused on communication skills and using the language in a real environment, has a positive effect on students' deeper understanding and use of the language, developing communication skills and cultural competence, while making the learning process more interesting.

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THE ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY IN DEVELOPING COMPENSATORY COMPETENCE IN PRIMARY SCHOOL LEARNERS

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***Abstract.** The work is devoted to the development of compensatory skills in order to teach a foreign language at a language university. Definitions of the terms "competence" and "linguistic competence" are given. The levels of foreign language proficiency are considered, including basic, intermediate and advanced levels. As the main goal of mastering a foreign language, it is proposed to consider foreign language communicative competence in all the diversity of its components, which include linguistic, sociolinguistic, discursive, compensatory and sociocultural.*

***Keywords.** Competence; compensatory competence; levels of language proficiency; components of compensatory competence; types of speech activity; teaching a foreign language.*

Introduction. Language proficiency involves the formation of two main types of competencies: linguistic, studied and described mainly by representatives of linguistics, and communicative, involving the choice and implementation of